

Achieving Sustainability in Development through Participation, Public Policy and Public Administration in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examines how public administration and public policy can be used to achieve sustainable development in a multifaceted way, that is, economically, environmentally politically and agriculturally in Nigeria. Though Nigeria is rich in material and other resources, it has not fared well in terms of development indices. Mismanagement, corruption and misplaced priorities still dog her development strides. In this paper our attempt therefore is to show that if Nigeria purposively harnesses the rich potentials in public policies and the administrative strategies that abound in the country, then the desired goal of development can be achieved. The objectives of the study are to discuss the roles of administrators and public policy formulators in achieving development in government. Without proper administration and policy, success cannot be achieved. It is through administration and policy that we can harness and put together the values derived from other areas. The paper also highlights some hindrances to development in Nigeria and suggested ways of improving them. The paper recommends that the agencies saddled with the responsibilities of policies implementation be allowed to follow the framework as given and to block or check the excesses of major key players who stand to divert or hinder the implementation of policies.

Key words: Sustainability, Development, Public Administration, Public Policy and Participation.

Résumé

Cet article examine comment l'administration publique et les politiques publiques peuvent être utilisées pour réaliser un développement durable d'une manière multiforme, c'est-à-dire, économiquement, écologiquement, politiquement et culturellement au Nigeria. Bien que riche en ressources matérielles et autres, le Nigéria ne va pas bien en termes d'indices de développement. La mauvaise gestion, la corruption et les priorités mal placées continuent de freiner ses progrès en matière de développement. Dans cet article, nous essayons donc de montrer que si le Nigeria exploite à dessein les riches potentiels des politiques publiques et les stratégies administratives qui abondent dans le pays, alors l'objectif souhaité de développement peut être atteint. Les objectifs de l'étude sont de discuter des rôles des administrateurs et des formateurs de politiques publiques dans la réalisation du développement au gouvernement. Sans une administration et une politique appropriée, le succès ne peut être atteint. C'est à travers l'administration et la politique que nous pouvons exploiter et rassembler les valeurs dérivées d'autres domaines. Cet article souligne également certains obstacles au développement du Nigeria et suggère des moyens de les améliorer. Cette étude recommande que les agences chargées des responsabilités de la mise en œuvre des politiques soient autorisées à suivre le cadre tel qu'il est donné et à bloquer ou vérifier les excès des principaux acteurs clés susceptibles de détourner ou d'entraver la mise en œuvre des politiques.

Mots-clés: Survivance économique, Développement, Administration publique, Politique publique et Participation.

Introduction

Since independence, Nigeria has been grappling with developmental issues and has put in many programmes geared towards the development of the nation. Successive governments have carried out various programmes towards development of the country. Sustainable development discussed in the work is efficient, meaningful and continuous acceleration of advancement in a multifaceted way, which is sustainable development in economic, environmental, agricultural, political and administrative dimensions. The question is how sustainable are these development programmes? However, the problem which hampers sustainable development in the different dimensions stated above is lack of monitoring.

Monitoring and evaluation of government programmes according to Eminue (2005) are very important elements in project implementation. They are to achieve good quality work and successful completion of projects within specified time limits. He said it is not formulating a good policy but the proper evaluation and monitoring of the programme are what count. In line with Eminue's view, Egonmwan, (2000) observed that evaluation and monitoring of programmes exhibit managerial efficiency in carrying out projects, monitoring its progress, obtaining a feedback to surmount any difficulties that would hinder the programme implementation. Egonmwan (2000) opines that evaluation and monitoring specifically, are undertaken to ensure effective policy execution by identifying and dealing with problems that arise during implementation in relation to original expectations. Ayo's (1987) definition agrees with Egonmwan that evaluation and monitoring are to review progress in implementation of projects to identify and eliminate bottlenecks. But we discovered that problems influencing bottlenecks in government programmes like National Directorate of Employment (NDE), Family Support Programme (FSP), Directorate of Food, Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI) all could not last because of wrong priority, inadequate assessment of targets, and problem of formulation of design. In Ikelegbe's view, evaluation and monitoring are done for redirection, modification of programmes to enhance performance where programmes seem to fail, rather government prefers to increase expenditure as a solution to performance failures. For him it is not increased expenditure, but perfunctory monitoring to determine problems and to proffer solution (Ikelegbe, 1994).

There is a popular saying that "Policy is at the mercy of the administrator", (Eminue, 2005) telling us that Administrators participate in the development of public policies. Public administration according to Duru(2010) implies the management of public business. Those who are engaged in the management of public affairs are seen as administrators, who ensure that government policies are implemented. By implication, the administrator is an important figure in the success of government programmes. This means the administrator must possess certain attributes to be able to carry out duties effectively. As explained by Edame (2006) good administrator makes for national development. For Iwe (1991) leadership (the administrator) is an indispensable element of any social organization. A leader (the administrator), co-ordinates the execution and implementation of policies in an organization. The quality of life, success, growth in productivity, growth in economic

activities in a society quite often hinges on the quality and degree of leadership therein. A country without efficient leadership (administrator) is usually doomed to exploitation, or stagnation, to chaos and a state of social disarray. Agba, Ogaboh, and Nkpoyen (2014) also affirm that the bane of development in a country hinges on the manner administration is conducted and managed.

Policies are government programmes of action geared towards the welfare of its citizens. They are realization of objectives of what government wants to do. They could be policy on education to give qualitative education to its citizens, on agriculture for sufficient food for the populace, or on environment which the administrator is to execute. A good administrator should be able to identify the need of the people as a mediator to the government and as policies are formulated to solve those problems, he makes sure that those policies are implemented. However, in most cases the execution of the programme has been a problem in Nigeria, as most programmes fail at implementation stage. These are always attributed to bad and incompetent administrators; perhaps it failed because there was no good and clear goal to guide the policy; also because of corruption by government officials who misuse funds and perform very poorly, or approve bad jobs because they have been bribed. In the end projects or programmes are not executed. These constitute bottlenecks to implementation, leading to the suffering of the people. (Ayo, 1987)

Development is seen as qualitative improvement in the living standard of people in the society. Osita (2001) opines that a country's level of development is simply the ultimate result of its economic performance. A country will develop if it strengthens its development plan, strategies and implementation. It is people (administrators) with good policies that will bring about these realizations through a strong implementation strategy which includes monitoring and evaluation to check unexpected events.

In this paper, our concern is how public administration and public policies are used to attain the policy put in place to achieve sustainability in development in government programmes for its citizens. Most government policies have failed during implementation. The question is how do we solve these problems? The answers will lead us into finding out ways of having good policies and administrative structure will lead the government to put in place programmes that will culminate in sustainability in development of government programmes.

Statement of the Problem

Gleaning through literature, we can conclude that the development we claim to have in Nigeria in terms of proving qualitative improvement in the living standard of the people is not providing answers to our societal needs. Nigeria is still plagued with developmental issues such as insecurity, poverty, disease and poor standard of living for the citizens, unemployment, lack of good education, lack of social amenities, etc. Nigeria is still grappling with problems of policy implementation. Numerous national programmes have been formulated; however, there has not been tangible result from implementation of past programmes. Programmes like Agricultural policy. Nyong (2005) explained that it was to increase agricultural output at minimum cost. Nyong affirmed that many strategies were put in place by the federal government to boost agricultural produce but Nyong lamented that agricultural policy did not fare well because of inadequacies in the supply and use of farm

inputs, shortage of working capital, lack of tractors, diverting of implements meant for agriculturalist. Health policy had its own constraints. These problems are replicated in other programmes. In summary, it is concluded that lack of policy framework as a guide to discover empirical facts continue to plague the country and these lead the country to a vicious circle of backwardness; lack of good leadership control and effective monitoring of policies also have led the country into failures of implementation of policies for sustainability in development for government programmes for the citizens.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study include to:

1. Identification of roles of Administrators and Public Policy formulators in achieving sustainability in development; and
2. To recommend effective development pathway for sustainability in development of government programmes.

Theoretical Framework

In this work we are using the integrated theory as our framework. This is because the issues of development are multifaceted. We are looking at development from the economic, environmental, agricultural, political and administrative dimensions. Foundationally, we cannot talk about development without the environment where the development takes place. This is how sustainability comes in. When the environment is taken care of as to make it enabling for other facets of development to take root, then we can have a balanced platform for implementation. The integrated theory is concerned with how to harness and integrate all productive forces in order to achieve balanced and sustainability in development of government programmes.

According to Abasiokong (1982) what is needed is to prioritize development issues by way of policy formulation and implementation. The environment, the economy, the politics, agriculture and administration are all important pillars in any quest for sustainability in development of government programmes. If administrators are unable to administer, the entire process of sustainability in development may not yield the desired result. In this wise our emphasis will be on policy and administration of all the incidental elements necessary for development.

As Adedeji (1991) opines development is a collective enterprise, therefore, steps have to be taken to make the process of development genuinely participatory thereby ensuring sustainability of the development process, the political, economic, administrative dimensions of development would have to be integrated in a manner that can optimize development possibilities. This is what this theory explains.

Conceptual Issues: Public Administration and Public Policy

Many people at different times have defined public administration from their own perspectives. Public administration is the organization and use of men and materials to accomplish a purpose. (Laxmikanth in Duru, 2014). Public Administrators have been said to be the implementers of public programmes and policies for holistic development of a nation which invariably means administrators are the organs used to implement the programmes. Agba et al (2014) clearly state that administrators are involved in the formulation and

execution of government policies/programmes and they can either slow it down or hasten its pace for a nation's development. Peter in Agba, et al (2014) agrees that implementation is a process of moving forward policy objectives by means of administrative steps. For Peter some of the factors hindering successful implementation of public policy and programme in Nigeria are administrative in nature. In Ikeji's view where there are no administrative capabilities in the system; there will inevitably be poor performance in government programmes. (Ikeji, 2002)

Administrators manage public affairs. They supervise, direct the running of government affairs. Administrators are the machinery as well as the integral process, through which government performs their functions. (Duru, 2014). They accomplish government programmes; they cause programmes to be realized in real life. This means administrators can make or mar any programme at their disposal. There is therefore the need for conducive environment to work, good work ethics, hard work, honesty on the part of the administrator.

Appadorai (2001) says administration is seen as the execution of policies and programmes that government has agreed to implement. The success of any government depends on how well these policies and programmes have been implemented. The discourses above suggest administration and policies are essential apparatus for the success of implementation of government programmes. Supporting Appadorai's view Duru(2014) explains that one cannot study public administration without the concept of public policy. Public policy is a programme of government to be carried out by the Administrator (Public administration). It is what government does, for example government may provide health centres in strategic locations for its citizens.

Anderson (1975) in Duru explains that public policy is what government actually does and not what they intend doing, meaning that mere declaration of intention, wishes, expression of desires cannot be regarded as public policies. Policies are put in place by the government to touch the lives of the masses, policies like Agricultural policy, environmental policy, educational policy and health policy. Drawing from Duru's definition Jenkins in Duru (2014) defines public policy as a set of interrelated decision by a political actor or group concerned with the selection of goals and means of achieving them within a specified situation where those decisions should in principle be within the powers of those actors . This definition according to Nyong is more appropriate because it recognizes the need for availability of means to achieve objectives as well as the competence of the persons(administrator) who are to take decision on behalf of other (the Public) for which the decision is being made. There has been policy of Agriculture, defence, education, housing. Education policy like Nyong explains aspires to serve as instruments for achieving rapid development, fostering national unity, national identity and national integration. Different educational reforms were put in place like the UPE launched in the Western Region in January 1955. In 1974, the Federal Government reintroduced UPE at National level to be implemented in 1976.This had set backs because the policy was poorly planned and implemented, the 6.3.3.4 came in 1982. All these failed because of lack of implementation. Meaning that the agency saddled (administrator) with these responsibilities did not set the right policies in motion necessary for the plan to succeed. However, an administrator may still fail if the government fails to provide the enabling financial and other support.

Agricultural policy was put in place to achieve increase in food production. Agricultural policies are very important because agriculture is necessary for most developing countries.

Agricultural policy was articulated in Nigeria in the 4th National Development Plan 1962-1968, 1970-1974, 1975-1980 and was implemented during the period 1960-1985 (i.e. the rolling plans) (Nyong, 2005). After the war in 1970, government adopted various policy instruments to make agriculture productive; these include provision of bank credit, manpower development training, and agriculture credit guarantee scheme fund in 1978. The agricultural sector faced setbacks despite all these instruments. The problems were discovered to be lack of manpower which stem down to human capacity (the administrator).

National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS) is the response to the development challenges of Nigeria. In 1999, most people grossly underestimated the extent of social, political and economic decay of the country. Since 1999, NEEDS has succeeded in stabilizing the polity, consolidated the democratic governance structure, and made modest progress in the social and economic spheres. Over the next few years (2003-2007), NEEDS will consolidate the achievements of the previous four years and lay a solid foundation for sustainable poverty reduction, employment generation, wealth creation, and value reorientation (Obasanjo,2004). We are in 2018, yet Nigeria has not achieved these goals.

Eminue (2005) noticed that policies in Nigeria fail at implementation stage or are having problems because of lack of follow-up on policies of past governments by succeeding administrators. This leads to inconsistency in policy and so developmental goals are not realised. When policies are not consistent, there is no way they will be sustained. When what is intended and expected is not materialized in performance it leads to failure. This is what Chijioke in Egonmwan(2000) meant when he says that an administrator without a definite programme, is like a traveller without destination, he may cover many kilometres yet not able to say categorically where he is going or how far he has gone because he was going without definite objectives. Policies should be the real show of achievement of the aim of government on programmes.

Policy on Development Plans in Nigeria

Development today poses a challenge and presents an opportunity for urgent reflection and action for our very survival (Dube, 2001). It is the quest for development that necessitated the need for planning. *Planning without Fact* by Stopler was written in the colonial era to help Nigeria come out of her development problems. It should be noted that, lack of planning, inadequate planning, or poor planning can be a great impediment to any developing nation, which can result to uneven development, poverty, political instability, stagnation.

Arua and Duru (2010) explained that Development plan started in Nigeria during the colonial era, when following the initiative of the Secretary of State for the Colonies, a ten year plan of Development and Welfare for Nigerians came into operation in 1946 by the colonial government under their Development and Welfare Fund. The major emphasis was on building, transportation and communication system. According to Ayo (1987), the plan could hardly be said to be a development plan, because it was more of a list of projects, the selection and preparing of the projects did not take into consideration the population being

planned for. The plan was just to facilitate the control of our resources. Following the creation of Regions in 1954, separate development programmes were prepared for the federal, Western, Eastern and Northern regions for the year 1955-60. These developmental programmes known as Economic Development Plans were later revised and extended to cover 1960-62 at an estimated total cost of #328 million during the five years. Since independence, in 1960, Nigeria has formulated and implemented comprehensive national development plans. The first National plan was from 1962-68 which major focus was on Agriculture, industry and training of manpower where many of the goals of the public sector were not achieved owing to the outbreak of the political crises in 1965, and the civil war in 1967.

The second National Development Plan was after the war in 1970-1974, the war ravaged places were to be rebuilt and reconstructed. There was high rate of immigration from rural to urban areas for search of better life. Governments focus on the problem of rehabilitating the people, boosting GDP and to revitalize abandoned projects. The third development plan 1980 was to increase per capita income. Money was needed to kick start the economy and to address the problem of marginalization which was the reason for the redistribution of income. The Fourth National plan 1985 was where Federal government took a holistic approach on housing by providing shelter, auxiliary services and community services such as provision of water supply, access road, sewage, refuse disposal, employment opportunities. This followed by the Fifth National Development Plan 1986-1990 with the focus on diversification from mono-cultural to revitalization of the agricultural sector to achieving self-sufficiency through integrated rural development programme, to encourage local industry so as to arrest mass unemployment problem. First National Rolling Plan of 1992 emphasized more on housing scheme which necessitated the training of personnel on technology for the production of durable materials from local sources and their uses for the construction of houses.(Aruaand Duru, 2010).

The Concept of Sustainable Development

The ultimate purpose of development must be the development of man and his society. (Adedeji 1991)The concept of sustainable development became a common language at the world's first Earth Summit in Rio in 1997. The Original definition of sustainable development is usually considered as development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of the future generation to meet their own needs. This is the ability to sustain, support, uphold, or confirm what is targeted or achieved. This is how natural systems function, remain diverse and produce everything it needs for the ecology to remain in balance. Sustainable development takes into account how we might live in harmony with the natural world around us, protecting it from damage and destruction. In this case the needs of the people must be given serious priority. People live in urban centres which require light, good roads, good buildings, which need improvement, so there is need to balance competing needs, meeting health needs, environmental needs, technological needs, economic needs. There is need to safeguard natural resources and agro ecological practices.

. The primary goals of sustainable development are:

- To end poverty and hunger
- To achieve better standards of education and health care.
- To achieve gender equality
- To achieve sustainable economic growth while promoting jobs and stronger economies
- All of the above and more while tackling the effect of climate change, pollution and other environmental factors that can harm and do harm to people's health, livelihood and lives. (World Development report, 1997).

Sustainable development is the ability to sustain, support, uphold natural system to remain diverse and produce everything it needs for the ecology to remain balanced, so that there are no compromises of the natural biotic system (Akpama, 2015). Akpama's definition according to Lukpata and Asha(2014) embodies two major concepts, the concepts of needs particularly the essential needs of the world's poor, which maximum priority should be given; and the concept of limitations imposed by the state of technology and social organization on the ability of the environment to meet the present and future needs. It acknowledges that civilization takes resources to sustain life. Yet there are countless examples throughout the human history where civilization has damaged its own environment and seriously affected its own survival changes. The case of Ogoni land and other Niger Delta regions in Nigeria are not left out in this discourse, where there have been major negative impacts on sustainable development on the environment and on existing social structures. Many traditional societies have been devastated by the lack of sustainable development of their forest resource, water systems, and intensive fisheries. Urban areas in developing countries commonly suffer from extreme pollution and inadequate transportation, water and sewer infrastructure. Environmental damage, if unchecked, may undermine the achievements of development and even lead to collapse of essential ecosystem as witnessed today in some parts of the country. Agreeing with this is the case of Ogoni land in River State.

Duru (1999) commenting on the issue of development as postulated by the Multi-National Corporations(MNCs) in Niger Delta, affirm that the role of MNCs in development of oil producing communities of Niger Delta is more of a myth than reality. According to Duru (1999) the sole objective of MNCs in Niger Delta is maximizing profit and not as purveyors of true development as seen in Ogoni crisis. The World Bank report confirms that the region's sustainable development remains unfulfilled and its future is threatened by deteriorating economic conditions. Sustainable development as postulated by World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987 is development that should meet the essential needs of the poor, but not the destruction brought by technology, with reckless exploitation of her natural resources. The idea was to make the earth pleasant for its inhabitant as explained by Akpama(2015) but in Niger Delta region the case is different. The World Bank report lamented that despite the vast oil reserve in Ogoni land, the region remains poor; the educational level in Niger Delta is below the average levels. Poverty level is high, cost of living is high, only few houses are considered structurally in order, waterborne diseases are common, electrification despite their enormous energy resources is poor, water supply, sanitation, social amenities are all poor. (Mitee in Duru, 1999). There has been extinction of traditional crops and tubers for agriculture, crops have stopped

growing in their soil, fish catch has dwindled, farm land are destroyed, flora and fauna and the environment are all destroyed. Their means of livelihood has been destroyed. Young jobless youths migrate from rural to urban centres yet there are no jobs for them because the oil money is not invested in the region but was channelled to other major towns and cities outside the region (Duru, 1999)

As explained by Akpama(2015) nations have been forced to disengage from careless exploitation of her natural resources that destroys the environment rather than protecting and conserving the environment. The Brundtland summit is rather aimed at making life and the earth conducive for its inhabitants. Their aspiration is to prevent policies that does not protect the environment but rather encourage good exploitation of natural resources. Thus policies are very essential; policies make or mar a nation. Good and monitored policies with a clear goal will produce good result for the development of the nation.

Participatory approach as the panacea for sustainable development

This approach emphasizes the role of people in planning, development and policy making. It entails the mobilization of people in the planning and programming of development strategies. This involves public awareness and a conscious effort in encouraging people's participation in the planning and policy process. In participatory approach, people's input are valued as important because it provides much information on their perceptions, needs, problems and opinions. Here there are open communication channels between the public and government. In participatory approach there is direct interaction between the planner and the masses in the formulation of policies and programmes. Some methods used in participatory approach are public hearings, referenda, public discussion, public information, public enlightenment programmes. (Ikelegbe, 2004). This approach according to Ikelegbe (2004) helps in the education of the public on government plans, programmes and activities. It is through this interaction that administration gets feedback from the people on the basic developmental infrastructure that the community needs. Especially infrastructure like rebuilding collapsed bridges, provision of water to the people, provision of light, hospitals, and schools.

The advocacy here is that beneficiaries of the programme should be made to participate in the programmes. They should participate fully both at the planning and the execution of the programme. They should be allowed to initiate their projects; they should be allowed to decide what they need because every community has priority needs of which they are pressing. A community may need electricity, culvert, school; a common agreement has to be reached as to which project most pressing is, which is the felt-need. If they all agree on culvert that becomes the felt-need and the project at the particular time (Ihejiamaizu, 2002).

Adedeji (1987) says it is only people who make development possible. Unless they participate fully in policy making they are not likely to be enthusiastic in the implementation. The human factor is the ultimate dialectics whereby people are necessarily and immutably the mentors of the processes of change and transformation and the beneficiaries of the result of such processes. Thus, our future policy on development must be human-centred and must be dedicated to the goal of ensuring the overall well-being of the people through the equitable distribution of the fruits of development" He explained that it is unacceptable to marginalize the people or the beneficiaries of the project in any

development process. He points out that one of the development challenges in nations was the neglect of the people who know the development strategies of the communities. We aver that a sound strategy for development must take into account the historical tradition of the people. Thus there is need to effectively involve the ordinary people in the decision that affect their lives. That development should not be undertaken on behalf of the people, but by them, it should be the organic outcome of society's value system, its perceptions, and its concerns and its endeavours so as to achieve sustained development.

Tanzania Arusha (Ujamaa villagization Programme, 1967) approach recommended people delineate for themselves their critical needs and to identify the remedial steps that the people are willing to take. When people are involved in projects that benefit them, they speed up the projects because there is good decision making and mutual trust. Their needs, concerns, problems and interests are expressed and considered. It enhances equity as government reacts to and balances of different interest and problems of various groups; it enhances public mobilization and commitment to programmes, which raise the people's support, confidence leading to programme possibilities and success. It provides motivation as people are willing to put in their best. They monitor the execution programme to its implementation stage. When we create opportunity for people to participate in that which they are stake holders, the natural tendency is that they will seek to protect and defend the fruitfulness and productivity of the business. They are also likely to work with commitment while seeing themselves as stakeholders. And this will lead to accountability as the leaders are made to account for whatever is happening at every stage. This means that appropriate skills and institutions are all effective.

Recommendations

- Administration is about quality of personnel, having round pegs in round holes, strategies, supervision, Implementation, assessment of outcomes. Policies should be supervised
- There should be feedback mechanism to follow up public policies.

All

All corruption fighting agencies should be empowered and made more effective, e.g. EFCC, ICPC.

- Make the ordinary people the architect of their own development. That it is through human creativity, initiative, capability and commitment that true development can be achieved. Quoting Drapper in Adedeji(1987) development means 'releasing human energy. It means providing an opportunity for people to make the maximum contribution to their own development and to the self-sustaining development of their communities.
- Government should choose administrators with who are hardworking, honest who have integrity and accountability.

Conclusion

As Adedeji (1991) urged, Nigeria should take a clue from the experience of Japan and the newly industrialized countries (NICs). For the Japanese miracle has been achieved by the Japanese people. Japan has very few natural resources, yet it is the fastest-growing large industrialized country in the world. The rapid transformation in the NICs has been rooted firmly in the determination and industry of the people of those countries through the development of small-scale enterprise, high savings and impressive productivity. He also talks on human development when you develop the human being you are releasing their energy and they will contribute to the development of the nation. Nigeria's case is that of gross mismanagement of the economy by the leaders. Good, efficient administration and policy cannot be over emphasized in the attainment of sustainable development in government programmes. The administrator guides, they are the instrument for executing government policies and programmes, they can through their wealth of knowledge and good leadership style bring about social change and economic development. They provide continuity when government changes either due to revolutions (Duru, 2014). Every organization has identifiable goals and it the administrator's duty to see that these goals are attained. Administration is concerned with the effort of goal realization. This is why Edame (2006)says a good administrator should be a good leader with good qualities. Adedeji(1991) mention human resource development, this implies the development of the administrator who will bring the potential in them for attainment of sustainability development of government programmes.

Nigeria according to Edame (2006) as one of the developing nation is faced with the problems of development that has to do with vicious cycle of poverty, high rate of illiteracy economic backwardness, political instability, and low level of unemployment. According to him, the development impacts of these countries were attributed to the leadership.

From the fore-going, we have pointed out many reasons why sustainability in development may remain an unfulfilled dream in Nigeria. However, this is not to say that there is no hope for Nigeria. We are recommending in this paper that the way out is through the adoption of participatory approach. There is the old saying that men are, at their best when set to work on that which is their own or in which they have vested interest. Apart from sound policy and implementation, a sustainable administration and incentivization of workers through inclusiveness and participatory approach is necessary. When this is done we are likely going to enhance productivity.

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